

CNN-Based Analysis and Classification of Fingerprint Patterns

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Abstract:- One of the most important biological parts of the human body is the fingerprint, which holds a lot of unique information. To enhance fingerprint recognition, a wide range of features and algorithms have been suggested. This research presents a comprehensive deep learning framework for fingerprint recognition using convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which can learn the feature representation and recognize the fingerprints simultaneously. Typically, the process of classification begins with the fingerprint image's features being extracted. These features are typically based on visual characteristics. This paper presents a method for classifying fingerprints using convolutional neural networks. The proposed approach was tested on collected KVK-R fingerprint dataset. We have employed an explicit feature extraction procedure by integrating image processing into the classifier's training. The approach produced excellent results with high accuracy rates. Using trained model for feature classification we achieved with 97.3% for KVK-R dataset.

Keywords: Fingerprint classification, Deep learning, convolutional neural network, fingerprint feature, Image enhancement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fingerprint recognition has become the most common form of biometric authentication. This is because fingerprints are unique, can be used by anyone, and don't change. The identification process involves finding the template fingerprint that matches the name of a fingerprint that has been entered in. In the last 20 years, many fingerprint matching and identification methods [1,2,3] have been produced. Their different features lead to many choices between efficiency and precision. Applications for fingerprint technology include forensics, transaction authentication, unlocking mobile phones, and more. Numerous fingerprint identification methods that have been proposed depend on matching details. Ridge ending, bifurcation, and short ridge are the three main minute characteristics of fingerprint ridges. One of the most widely used methods to accomplish this is fingerprint classification. The input fingerprint is classed before it is identified, and multiple classes of fingerprints are established. After then, only templates from the predicted class are compared to it [4].

Traditionally, each template fingerprint in the database is manually labeled by an expert. Next, using the labelled dataset that was obtained, the classifier is trained to assign the same label which was manually established for each input fingerprint to each matching template. This is a lengthy process that requires human involvement. Additionally, a number of studies on fingerprint identification utilizing manually created characteristics and subsequent categorization have been conducted in the past[5].

So far, a number of fingerprint classification strategies have been presented each based on a different feature set that includes orientation maps [6], singular points [7], ridge structure [8], filter-based response [9], and various extraction techniques. General-purpose classification algorithms like Support Vector Machines (SVMs) [10] and k nearest-neighbors (k-NN) [11] are used in the majority of approaches. Some offer predefined classification guidelines that eliminate the need for a training process.

Recently deep learning has emerged as the standard method in the field of biometric recognition due to its ability to effectively process intricate and high-dimensional data. The integration of deep neural networks in biometric systems has led to significant enhancements in both accuracy and their robustness. Multiple research papers have investigated the utilisation of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for the purpose of analysing fingerprints[12]. A study employed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to identify the difference between genuine and fake fingerprints[13]. A different research conducted an experiment where Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were employed with randomly initialised weights, along with the utilisation of Local Binary Patterns (LBP) for feature extraction[14]. In addition, a technique was suggested that employs Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to categorise fingerprints and reduce the burden on databases, resulting in a 99% accuracy rate on the NIST-DB4 dataset. Another study shown that convolutional neural networks (CNNs), specifically those utilising the VGG16 architecture, have strong performance in accurately classifying fingerprint images with varied levels of quality[15]. Typical problems encountered in fingerprint pictures include moisture, blurriness, dryness, spots, and damage to the skin. In the experiment, two pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models, namely VGG-F and VGG-S, were utilised for fingerprint classification. The enhancement of these networks was achieved by the utilisation of the NIST-DB4 database and the application of transfer learning. The VGG-S received the good precision and accuracy rates on obtained data[16].

This study we presents a deep learning framework for fingerprint recognition in situations when there are limited samples available for each class, often known as few-shot learning. The system may take fingerprint images and use the previously preprocessed images for recognition. To complete the classification procedure, features are taken out of the proposed model and combined with a softmax classifier [17].

The own generated KVK-R fingerprint datasets is used to train a convolutional neural network. We also use data augmentation methods to add more examples for each class, like flipping, random cropping, and introducing tiny amounts of distortions. We can achieve a remarkably high

rate of accuracy in recognizing the test samples of this dataset. We are sure that this framework has the potential to be extensively utilized for any other biometric identification task.

II. THE PROPOSED APPROACH

1.1 Deep learning

In recent years, Deep Learning has produced exceptional achievements in a variety of application sectors, including image processing and computer vision. A CNN-based technique was used to tackle the fingerprint classification problem[18]. On the other hand, manual feature extraction and image quality changes provide a challenge to typical minutiae-based approaches. Using CNNs for automated feature extraction and classification, we provide a deep learning-based method to overcome these drawbacks. With this approach, fingerprint classification systems will be more accurate and robust, able to deal with changes in the quality of fingerprint images.

Conventional techniques for classifying fingerprints depend on symmetric and morphological traits derived from local fingerprint substructures. Most systems only use the two most notable structures [19]—Ridge Ending and Ridge Bifurcation, often known as minutiae—which correspond to the terminations and bifurcations of the ridges, respectively—since it is difficult to identify them and because some of them are quite similar to one another[20].

In the area of image recognition and classification, deep learning has been shown to be an effective tool, far exceeding traditional methods. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have demonstrated remarkable potential in fingerprint classification because of their capacity to automatically extract and learn hierarchical characteristics from unprocessed fingerprint pictures. This section explores the CNN architecture, feature extraction procedure, and classification method in detail as it relates to the deep learning strategy suggested for fingerprint classification [21].

Figure 1. The proposed CNN learning structure for image classification task.

2.2 Fingerprint image classification using CNN

In the study we focused on fingerprint image classification task by employing proposed cnn model. A CNN model containing multiple convolutional, pooling and dropout layers comprises the basis of the suggested deep learning methodology which is shown in fig.1. Convolutional layers automatically identify and extract features that are necessary, like patterns, textures, and edges. Pooling layers minimize computational effort while preserving important information by shrinking the spatial dimensions of the feature maps. By randomly changing a portion of the

input units to zero during training, dropout layers are used to prevent overfitting. The combination of these elements creates an effective framework that improves fingerprint classification's accuracy[22,23].

Convolutional Layers: These layers use several filters to apply convolution operations to the input images. Every filter aids in the detection of several fingerprint-specific characteristics, including edges, textures, and patterns. The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function, which adds non-linearity to the model and helps it learn complicated patterns, comes after the convolutional operation.

Pooling Layers: The spatial dimensions of the feature maps are decreased by using pooling layers, especially MaxPooling. Performing so, the computational load decreases while the most important aspects are retained. MaxPooling layers choose the maximum value from each feature map region to capture the most significant elements presented in fig.2(b).

Flatten Layer: This layer takes 2D feature maps and transforms into a 1D vector so that it may be fed into layers which are fully connected shown in fig.2(a).

Fully Connected Layer: A fully connected layer that creates a final feature vector by combining the extracted features. This layer typically has a large number of neurons which analyze the features further using the ReLU activation function[5,24].

Figure 2. Feature map of 2D convolution(a) and Max pooling layer(b).

III. FEATURE EXTRACTION AND CLASSIFICATION

Features of fingerprint images are taken from the output of previously processed images. The suggested approach is dependent on specific algorithms. edge detection comes after the enhancement of fingerprint images with the use of Gaussian Blur and Thresholding techniques to improve image quality. Following this, the minutiae features are extracted with a specific focus on ridge ends and bifurcations shows in fig.3. Once the features are extracted, and then they are fed in to the softmax classifier. The final feature vector is transformed by the softmax layer into a collection of probabilities, each of which indicates the chance that the input fingerprint is a member of a particular class. The model's ability to effectively handle multi-class classification is ensured by this probabilistic method[25].

Figure 3. Minutiae features extraction i.e. bifurcations and ridge endings from skeleton image

IV. TRAINING AND EVALUATION

The proposed model train on own generated KVK-R fingerprint dataset with large number of subject along with multiple image samples of per subject with different iteration. In order to improve accuracy, we provide a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model for fingerprint classification in this work. L2 regularization and dropout are also included. In order to downsample the feature maps, the architecture consists of multiple convolutional layers (32, 64, and 128 filters) with ReLU activation and max-pooling layers (2x2). In order to minimize overfitting, dropout layers with 0.25 and 0.5 rates are added. Additionally, the training process is stabilized by adding a thick layer with 128 units and L2 regularization (factor 0.01). Softmax activation is used in the final output layer to classify the data. The fingerprint classification performance is enhanced by this architecture, which minimizes overfitting and ensures efficient feature learning. The performance of the model was evaluated using the metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The result of confusion matrix shown in fig.4(b). A high score on these measures, especially an accuracy rate of up to 97.3%, shows in fig.4(a) that the model is good at correctly classifying fingerprints[17].

Figure 4. (a) Validation of training and testing accuracy (b) Visualize confusion matrix plot.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study offers a strong methodology for fingerprint classification that combines typical image enhancing techniques with modern deep learning models. The system assures high-quality input for subsequent processing by using Gaussian Blur, Thresholding, and edge detection for initial picture enhancement, as well as focusing on minutiae feature extraction. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), particularly through designs like VGG16 and pre-trained models such as VGG-F and VGG-S, have shown significant improvements in accuracy and robustness across a variety of fingerprint datasets, including NIST-DB4. Furthermore, the proposed deep learning architecture, when combined with data augmentation approaches and trained on the collected KVK-R fingerprint dataset, receives outstanding accuracy even in few-shot learning settings. Experimental findings show the model's better performance with great accuracy in fingerprint classification even in cases of image quality fluctuations. This method offers a consistent and effective solution for biometric identification systems, therefore greatly improving the condition of fingerprint classification.

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